

Recommended citation: Mulligan, B., de la Torre, L., Pozzo, M. I., Foss, A., & Nilsson, K. (2020). The Potential of Online Laboratories in STEM Education; First Steps Towards an International Community of Practice. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1348-1354). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654330.

THE POTENTIAL OF ONLINE LABORATORIES IN STEM EDUCATION; FIRST STEPS TOWARDS AN INTERNATIONAL COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

B. Mulligan

Institute of Technology Sligo
Sligo, Ireland

L. de la Torre,

UNED,
Madrid, Spain.

M.I. Pozzo

National University of Rosario
Rosario, Santa Fe, Argentina

Angela Foss

Southern New Hampshire University
Manchester NH, USA

Kristian Nilsson

Blekinge Institute of Technology
Karlskrona, Sweden

Conference Key Areas: e-learning, niche and novel topics

Keywords: *Online laboratories, remote laboratories, virtual laboratories, distance education*

ABSTRACT

Access to practical laboratory exercises has always been a challenge in STEM education and is even more of a problem in online or distance learning programmes. In this paper, some training demands in STEM, related to experimentation and the operation of equipment, and the ways in which distance education can contribute to them are systematized. After a brief description of the different forms, some experiences that have been implemented in different parts of the world are compiled. It will also describe efforts that are underway to create an international community to share ideas, equipment and carry out collaborative research into the possibilities and impact of these efforts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Distance education has always had more significant challenges in engineering because of the need to meet learning outcomes in experimental methods and in the operation of physical equipment. This has, in the past been dealt with by compulsory residency requirements or in a limited number of cases by creating kits that can be posted out to students. The objective of this paper is to argue for the benefits of remote access to laboratory and other practical learning experiences (including simulations) and the need for creating an international community of practice dedicated to this topic. It will describe the scale of the challenge and the consequent benefits of building an international community of practice and how technology can help in both the creation of individual learning experiences and in building a community. It will list examples of existing networks in this domain and argue that a wider more inclusive network is required and describe the work completed to date in creating that community.

2 MOTIVATION

2.1 Challenges for remote and campus learning

It should be noted that access to laboratories is also an issue for residential students as well as remote learners, due to expense, safety and other issues. They may only have access to a limited range of equipment and for very limited periods of time [1] often resulting in graduating students who do not have the full complement of skills they need. Also, from a pedagogical point of view, students may not: 1) have the time required to investigate various scenarios of particular phenomenon to improve understanding and develop research skills, 2) be properly laboratory sessions and 3) feel comfortable enough working with certain systems due to safety hazards in some experiments.

2.2 Online laboratory access can help

It is clear, therefore, that facilitating online access to practical learning experiences can help improve the quality of learning of both distance and campus learners [2, 3, 7]. 'Online laboratories' is a term that comprehends many forms of experiences mediated by technologies. Certain types of online labs are: virtual laboratories (or simulations), remote, hybrid and digitized. Simulations have been used successfully to improve understanding of phenomena. Some research indicates that less time spent on physical equipment along with more time spent in simulators leads to both better understanding and recall [13]. Research on cognitive and social psychology applied to STEM education and learning has triggered a crucial shift from teacher to student-centred pedagogic approaches as from the mid 20th century today [14], [15]. Virtual laboratories that visually reproduce experiences may well improve learning outcomes even further, but these are much more expensive and time consuming to develop.

Many educators believe that for certain learning outcomes remote access to real physical equipment may be the best solution as they not only familiarise the student with the equipment that they may use in the workplace, they also replicate many of the errors and challenges in using real equipment that are not necessarily apparent in mathematical or visual simulations but are more expensive and difficult to set up than normal laboratories. Other perceived drawbacks of remote labs are the student to student interactions that occur within a lab setting [16].

Digitized Laboratories represent a compromise between Virtual and Remote. These applications use real data collected previously from a range of experiments and replicate the normal errors in experimental measurement. Some advantages when compared to remote ones include: 1) concurrent users, 2) minimal maintenance costs and 3) constant availability. Disadvantages include: 1) time required and difficulty in collecting the required data, 2) some experiments present just too many possible configurations and states to be able to get a complete and trustworthy enough data set. Hybrid also represents a compromise between Virtual and Remote. These labs combine the use of mathematical models and simulations to represent an equipment, system or process with real actuators and devices to perform control operations that, instead of being transmitted to real-world processes are applied to the simulated system. The main advantage of this approach is that this type of online lab is cheaper, but they inherit several disadvantages from virtual and remote labs.

2.3 The scale of the challenge

Whereas the creation of one online practical learning experience may be possible for a single professor or small team in a reasonable period, this is not feasible for a full course or multiple courses. For an institution, the challenge is several orders of magnitude greater.

2.4 International Community of Practice

In view of the scale of the challenge it is clear that there are significant benefits in sharing. For that reason, this paper is proposing the formation of an International Community of Practice. This approach consists in a collaborative activity [17] through different modes of sharing [18,19]. The use of ICT in education has led to the creation of online communities of practices, which may refer to very particular learning experiences by virtual encounters to foster global citizenship and an international orientation in education [20]. This community of practice is essentially about sharing knowledge (as opposed to creating knowledge). It should be noted that the core objective is not to necessarily to create online versions of lab experiences but the achievement of practical and experimental learning outcomes which are achieved in a campus laboratory experience. Members will be interested in any workable solutions that can allow their remote students achieve these outcomes.

The main objective of the community would be to collaboratively share and structure a database of solutions in a way that can easily be searched. These would include the following:

- Designs for remotely accessible experimental rigs
- Remotely accessible rigs that are available to other institutions.
- Freely and commercially available simulations, Virtual Labs and Digitized Labs.
- Designs for kits that can be assembled and posted to students.
- Commercially available kits and suppliers that assemble customised kits or provide technological solutions for developing and deploying online labs.
- Designs for home or work-based exercises based on widely available materials.
- Student-centered design strategies and best practices

2.5 Existing networks

A small number of such networks already exist, many concentrating on a subset of the objectives listed above or confined to specific regions or domains.

- European funded project Go-Lab (<https://www.golabz.eu/>): This site offers a collection of online labs (mostly virtual, and some remote) and try-out interactive inquiry apps.
- European funded project PILAR (<http://pilar.ieec.uned.es:8282/aboutus>) proposes a solution to the widespread use of VISIR [8] remote laboratory, as the mounting components on the relay switching matrix is limited due to the limited number of nodes and component boards. The project aims to interconnect all VISIR systems with each other in order to create a grid laboratory shared and accessed by all the participants, expanding and empowering existing systems to a new level of service and capacity. This allows expanding the application range: each university may install certain circuits on its own VISIR and utilize another type of circuits installed on a VISIR of other universities and vice versa.
- Spanish Network UNILabs (<https://unilabs.dia.uned.es/>): This network is formed by Spanish universities primarily and focuses on control systems online laboratories in the form of both virtual and remote ones. The main objective of the network is to share the online labs among the universities that are part of the network.
- Open University's OpenSTEM (<http://stem.open.ac.uk/study/openstem-labs>)
- India's Virtual Lab (<http://www.vlab.co.in/>): A country-level effort promoted by the government of India to provide virtual labs to universities and high schools in India.
- Thomas Bata University's ISES Remlab Net : 18 remote labs on different fields of Physics, freely accessible. (<https://www.ises.info/index.php/en/laboratory>)

- Open Source Physics (<https://www.compadre.org/osp/>): The OSP collection of the COMPADRE library provides curriculum resources, in the form of simulations, that engage students in physics, computation, and computer modeling.
- Colorado University's PhET (<https://phet.colorado.edu/>): Another free collection of interactive math and science simulations, similar to the OSP project. PhET simulations (158 are available at the moment) are based on extensive education research and their focus is to engage students through an intuitive, game-like environment where they learn through exploration and discovery.

Despite their many differences, all the above networks have something in common: they focus on sharing online lab end applications rather on promoting, discussing and sharing tools for developing your own labs for remote learners, good practices, experiences and so on. Many feel that there may be even more benefits to building a worldwide community of practice particularly for individuals who wish to share ideas, and resources with others in their own subject or sub-domain. Such networks benefit significantly from scale and as there are so many sub-domains this approach is more likely to be successful if it covers the largest population possible.

2.6 Building a sustainable community of practice

Many virtual communities of practice already exist and many of these have been able to operate on a totally voluntary basis with minimal costs incurred. The Internet essentially lowers the financial barriers to entry. At the time of writing, a LinkedIn group, "Labs for Remote Learners", has been formed with approximately 270 members (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12072791/>). Should this community prove to be useful to STEM educators, it will most likely need to move to a financial footing at some point. However, as online communities of practice can be very lean, it need not necessarily require paid membership. It may be that it can become financially sustainable through grants, running events and sponsorship.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

More flexible and cost-effective access to education is a worthwhile objective. While there has been significant progress in achieving the learning outcomes of normal classroom practices online, facilitating practical and experimental work has been more challenging. The range of topics where flexible solutions are required is such that no individual academic or institution can address this on their own. It is the authors' hope that by building an online Community of Practice we can make it easier for individuals and institutions to help both their remote and campus students to better achieve practical and experimental learning outcomes.

REFERENCES

- [1] Colwell C., Cooper E.S.S. (2002) "Using Remote Laboratories to Extend Access to Science and Engineering", *Computers & Education*, vol. 38, pp. 65-76
- [2] Hesselink, L., Rizal, D. , Bjornson,E., Paik, S. , Batra, R., Catrysse,P. , Savage, D. and Wong, A. (2003) "Stanford cyberlab: Internet assisted laboratories," *International Journal of Distance Education Technologies*.
- [3] Aktan, B., Bohus, C. A., Crowl L. A. and Shor,M. H., (1996) "Distance learning applied to control engineering laboratories", *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 1996, vol. 39, n° 3, pp. 320-326.
- [4] Rodriguez Triana, M. J., Govaerts, S., Halimi, W., Holzer, A. C., Salzmann, C., Vozniuk, A., de Jong, T., Sotirou, S., and Gillet, D., (2014) "Rich Open Educational Resources for Personal and Inquiry Learning. Agile Creation, Sharing and Reuse in Educational Social Media Platforms", *International Conference on Web & Open Access to Learning*, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, November 25-27
- [5] Kolb, U., Brodeur, M., Braithwaite, N. S., and Minocha, S., (2018) "A robotic telescope for university-level distance teaching", *Robotic Telescopes, Student Research and Education Proceedings*, vol. 1, n. 1, pp. 127–136
- [6] Chacon, J., Saenz, J., de la Torre, L., Diaz, J. M., and Esquembre, F., (2017) "Design of a Low-Cost Air Levitation System for Teaching Control Engineering", *Sensors*, vol. 17, n. 10, pp. 2321-2339
- [7] de la Torre, L., Sanchez J. P., and Dormido, S., (2016) "What Remote Labs can do for you", *Physics Today*, vol. 69, pp. 48-53
- [8] Evangelista, I.; Farina, Cadierno, M.; Roldán, G.; Pozzo, M.I.; Dobboletta, E.; García Zubía, J.; Hernández, U.; Alves, G.; Marchisio, S.; Concari, S.; Nilsson, K. (2018). Active learning on DC circuits: spreading the use of VISIR remote lab in Argentina. *Proceedings of the World Engineering Education Conference (EDUNINE 2018) pp.1-6*. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE). ISBN: 978-1-5386-4889-6. Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8450966>
- [9] Available online at: <https://www.golabz.eu/>
- [10] Available online at: <https://unilabs.dia.uned.es/>
- [11] Alves, G., Fidalgo, A., Marques, A., Viegas, C., Felgueiras, M., Dobboletta, E. (2016). Spreading remote labs usage: A System – A Community – A Federation. In <https://doi.org/10.1109/CISPPEE.2016.7777722> (Ed.), 2nd International Conference of the Portuguese Society for Engineering Education (CISPPEE2016). Vial Real
- [12] Available online at: <https://site.ieee.org/sagroups-edusc/>
- [13] Viegas, C.; Pavani, A.; Lima, N.; Marques, M.; Pozzo, M.I.; Dobboletta, E.; Atencia, V.; Barreto, D.; Calliari, F.; Fidalgo, A.; Lima, D.; Temporão, G.; Alves, G.R. (2018). Impact of a Remote Lab on Teaching Practices and Students Learning. *Computers & Education (Elsevier)*, 126, 201–216. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360131518301878?via%3Dihub>
- [14] J. E. Froyd, P. C. Wankat and K. A. Smith, "Five Major Shifts in 100 Years of Engineering Education," in *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 100, no. Special Centennial Issue, pp. 1344-1360, 13 May 2012, doi: 10.1109/JPROC.2012.2190167.

- [15] Phillip C. Wankat, Frank S. Oreovicz. Teaching Engineering. Purdue University 2007
- [16] Lal, S., Lucey, A., Lindsay, E., Treagust, D., Mocerino, M., Long, J., Zadnik, M., (2018) "The Effects of Remote Laboratory Implementation on Freshmen Engineering Students' Experience", American Society for Engineering Education, Paper ID #22272.
- [17] Wenger, E. (1998) *Communities of Practice: Learning, Meaning, and Identity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [18] Klein, J. H. (2005) "Knowledge characteristics of communities of practice." *Knowledge Management Research & Practice* 3: 106–14.
- [19] Amin, A. and Roberts, J. (2008) "Knowing in action: beyond communities of practice." *Research Policy* 37(2): 353–69.
- [20] Schwarz-Bechet, B. Bos-Wierda, R. and Barendsen, R. (2012). Transatlantic Online Community of Practice. *The International Conference on E-Learning in the Workplace* 2012. Available at https://www.ielassoc.org/docs/research/Schwartz_Bos-Wierda_ICELW2012.pdf